

STUDY OF SHWITRA YOGA IN THE TREATMENT OF LEUCODERMA / VITILIGO

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Article Received on 15 Sept. 2025,

Article Revised on 30 Sept 2025,

Article Published on 15 Oct. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17439598>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Deodatta Bhadlikar, Dr. Devyani Bhadlikar, Dr. Shruti Saxena*, Dr. Archana Pandey Jumle, Rahul Jumle. (2025). STUDY OF SHWITRA YOGA IN THE TREATMENT OF LEUCODERMA / VITILIGO. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(20), 1158-1166.

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda has described a number of “Asadhya” diseases, Leucoderma is one of them and is a medico-social Problem since the time of Bhagavan Manu. Manu has said, even if one’s daughter is suffering from Leucoderma she should be kept away from marriage for the sake of society. Although the disease is not contagious or there is no pain or complications in this disease.

According to Ayurveda, Leucoderma is a disease difficult to cure by its very nature. So it is a difficult task for the patients as well as “Chikitsaka”.

We were inspired to take the challenge of this disease to society and we selected the Problem of Leucoderma.

In initial stage we started a pilot study of different drugs which are described in the text books of Ayurveda as a “Kushthagha”.

Out of which we selected-six drugs for our trial. We prepared a combination of it and we administered in several patients. We found very encouraging results with this trial, and we think to carry out this trial on more patients scientifically and methodically, The combination of six drugs named as a Shwitra -Yoga on which we started some systematic work.

METHOD AND MATERIALS

Under the trial of Shwitra-yoga, patients were examined according to the Ayurvedic concept of tridosha and etiological factors etc. before treatment some specific proformas were filled up and then patients of Leucoderma were 'selected for "Shodhana" or "Shamana" type of treatment. Patients selected for Shodhan treatment were well explained about 'Shodhan' type of treatment and its importance. After getting consent from patients for Shodhana treatment, they were given 'Vamana' or and Virechana. Then they were given Shwitra-Yoga.

According to the concept of Ayurvedic treatment those patients of Shaman Sadhya type & others those were not ready to undergo "Shodhana" treatment were directly put on Shwitra-yoga. Along with this, for the associate symptoms like constipation, Krimi, were given symptomatic treatment accordingly.

The follow-up checking was carried out for a duration of fortnight to 1 month regularly with Vitiligo graph. At the end of every 15 days or 30 days the spots of Leucoderma were examined and the change in colour, margins, Pigmentations, size were observed and noted and the specific proforma were filled up.

What is Switra -Yoga?

Shwitra Yoga contains 6 drugs.

1. Bakuchi 2, Aamalaki 3, Anantmula 4. Tulsi, 5. Vidanga & 6. Ajamoda in which Bakuchi is in 2 parts and rest of the drugs eachare in 1 part, Details of the above six drugs are given in Table No. 7.

Tablets of Shwitra -Yoga containing 70 mg. are prepared and the dose of that tablet was fixed 6 to 9 per day. i.e. 2 to 3 tablets) Total 420 mg. to 630 mg.) per day tds, with Khadirjal. Oil Somaraji was given for local application to the patients under trial of Shwitra-Yoga.

OBSERVATION

Total 32 cases of Leucoderma were studied out, out of which 9 patients were given Vamana, 5 patients were given Virechan and 18 patiente were directly given Shwitra Yoga.

According to the age group, cast and sex group the details is are under

Out of total cases 14 patients were male and 18 patients were female. One patient was Muslim and 31 patients were Hindus. (Please see Table No. 1 and 2.)

We have not select patients below 5 years of the age.

We carried out that trial on 2 patients between the age of 5 to 10 years.

6 patients between the age of 10 to 15 years.

5 patients between the age of 15 to 20 years.

8 patients between the age of 21 to 25 years.

1 patient between the age of 26 to 30 years.

5 patients between the age of 31 to 35 years.

2 patients between the age of 36 to 40 years,

2 patients between the age of 41 to 45 years.

1 patient between the age of 46 to 50 years, age of group. (Please see Table No. 1)

According to chronicity the details are as below. (Please see Table No.3). We had taken the trial of patients suffering from Leucoderma from duration of

1 to 6 months 3 patients

7 to 12 months 4 patients

13 to 24 months 5 patients.

4 to 3 years Nil patients.

4 to 4 years 4 patients.

4 to 5 years 1 patient.

4 to 6 years 1 patient,

4 to 7 years 3 patients.

4 to 8 years 2 patients.

4 to 9 years Nil patient.

4 to 10 years 3. patients.

11 to 15 years 2 patients,

16 to 20 years 2 patients.

21 to 25 years 1 patient and

26 to 30 years 1 patient.

Total 32 patients

We did not find any patient above the duration of 30 years.

Looking to the history of patients taken under trial, 24 patients were previously undergone with various Allopathic medicines, 19 patients were undergone with other Ayurvedic treatment. 3 patients were undergone with Homoeopathic treatment and one patient was treated with Nature Cure treatment.

We also found II patients with the family history of Leucoderma.

Prognosis as described in Ayurveda it is found that 8 patients were “Sadhya” type 11 Patients were ‘Kasta Sadhya’ type and 13 patients were ‘Asadhya’ type out of 32 cases. (Please see Table No, 4).

There was past history of Vibandha (constipation) observed in 15 cases, history of Krimi (Worms) observed in 10 cases, history of Santat Jwara, (typhoid) observed in 8 cases, history of Visham Jwara (Malaria) observed in 7 cases, history of Kamala (Jaundice) observed in 4 cases, history of Pravahika (dysentery) observed in 3 cases and history of Arsha (Piles) observed in 2 cases, The history of Madhumeha (Diabetes mellitus), Aamvata (Rheumatism) Apasmar (Epilepsy) and Amla piita (hyper acidity) was found each in one case.

After completion of the trial of Shwitra-Yoga, six grades were given according to the result.

Grade 1 (G1) 100% improvement

Grade 2 (G.2) 75% improvement

Grade 3 (G 3) 50% improvement

Grade 4 (G.4) 25% improvement

Grade 5 (G.5) 0% improvement

Grade 6 (G-6) No improvement but increased.

Table No. 6 is given here for the purpose of result.

During the trial of Shwitra-Yoga in Leucoderma looking to the past history of Vibandha (constipation), Krimi, Visham Jwar (Malaria), Santat Jwar (Typhoid), Kamala (Jaundice) and Arsha (Piles), which were found in most of the cases, which are related with the digestive system, It can be established that Leucoderma has close relationship with digestive system and ‘Agni’.

Table 1: Showing the Age – Sex.

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
1 to 5 year	0	0	0
6 to 10 year	0	2	2
11 to 15 year	2	4	6
16 to 20 year	2	3	5
21 to 25 year	4	4	8
26 to 30 year	0	1	1
31 to 35 year	2	3	5
35 to 40 year	1	1	2
41 to 45 year	2	0	2
More than 46 year	1	0	1
Total	14	18	32

Table 2: Showing the distribution of Caste.

Caste	No. of Patients
Hindu	31
Muslims	1
Total	32

Table 3: Showing the Chronicity.

Period	No. of Patients
1 to 6 months	3
7 to 11 months	4
upto 2 years	5
upto 3 years	0
upto 4 years	4
upto 5 years	1
upto 6 years	1
upto 10 years	8
More than 10 years	6
Total	32

Table 4: Showing the Prognosis.

	Curable	Difficult to cure	Uncurable	Total
Patient No.	8	11	13	32

Table 5: Showing the Past Illness.

Disease	Constipation	Krimi	Typhoid	Malaria	Jaundice	Dysentery
%age	34.31	31.25	25.0	21.0	12.5	12.5
No. of Patients	15	14	8	7	4	4

Table 6: Showing the Result.

Grade No. of Patients	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6
%age	18.75	6.35	21.87	34.37	12.5	6.35

Table 7: Showing the contents of Shwitra –Yoga.

No.	Name of Drug	Latine Name	Ras	Vipak	Guna	Virya	Karma
1.	Bakuchi	Psoralia corylifolia Linn.	katu Tikta	Katu	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Krimighna Twak dosha nashak Kushthaghna Kandughna Shwitra prashaman para Keshya Twachya Rasayan Hridya
2.	Aamalaki	Embllica officinalis	Pancharas Except	Madhur	Laghu Ruksha	Shita	Rasayan Vayasthapan Kushthaghna

		Gaertn	Lavana		Shita		Krimighna Tridosahar
3.	Tulasi	Ocimum Sanctum Linn	Katu Tikta	Katu	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Kushthagha Krimighana hridya
4.	Aajamoda	Apium Graveolens Linn	Katu Tikta	Katu	Laghu Ruksha Tikshna	Ushna	Krimighna Deepan
5.	Aanatmul	Hemidesmus Indicus R. Br.	Madhur Tikta	Madhur	Guru Snigdha	Shita	Tridosh Nashak Rakta shodhak Kushthagha
6.	Vidanga	Embelia ribes Burm f.	Katu	Katu	Laghu Ruksha Tikshna	Ushna	Shrestha - Krimighna Kushthahar

DISCUSSION

Disease Leucoderma can appear at any age. We found 25 cases between the age group of 10 to 35 years of age. (78.12% Therefore during this age-group patients were aware of this disease, Patients those who come for the treatment had great worry for social or family Problem.

Leucoderma occurs in both the sex equal but more female patients come for the treatment, As they were more worried and conscious about their marriage problem as well as personal beauty.

The more number of patients came for treatment after doing allopathic and other Ayurvedic treatment. We found encouraging results with the trial of Shwitra-Yoga. The statistical data of its results are given below.

In 6 patients 100% improvement

In 2. patients 72% improvement

In 7 patients 50% Improvement

In 11 patients 25% improvement.

In 4 patients no cure observed and

2 patients showed increase of 6.35% spots with the trial of Shwitra-Yoga.

In Shwitra-Yoga the main drug is Bakuchi, Charaka and another ancient Ayurvedic physician had suggested Bakuchi in the treatment of Leucoderma. Bakuchi is successful drug for the treatment of Leucoderma. Moreover we mixed another five drugs with Bakuchi to strengthen its effect and to avoid its side-effect.

It is observed that the drug Shwitra-Yoga is successful in most of the cases of Leucoderma,

SUMMARY

With the treatment of Shwitra-Yoga 18.75% patients were completely improved.

6.25% patients 75% improved

21.87% patients 50% improved

34.37% patients 55% improved. These are encouraging results for further research.

The results of the trial of Shwitra-Yoga indicated that Shwitra-Yoga is successful drug for the treatment of Leucoderma.